

Comparison Of Eastern And Western Work Stressors (A STUDY OF WORK STRESSORS IN SOCIAL SECTOR OF PESHAWAR)

Author's Details:

- (1) **Maryam Bibi**, Phd Scholar at Abasyn University, Peshawar
(2) **Azhar Khan**, Astt Professor/ Joint Director Institute of Social Policy & Research (ISPaR), Peshawar
(3) **Farah Nadir** Lecturer in Home Economics Govt Frontier College Peshawar.
(4) **Fahad Ali khan** -Astt. Professor Northern University, Nowshera KP, Pakistan
(5) **Mohammad Ilyas**- MA Sociology University of Peshawar
(6) **Zia ur Rehman**- Lecturer Bacha Khan University Charsadda, KP, Pakistan

Abstract

The aim of this study is to find out work stressors according to their priority in the social sector (NGO's INGO's and CBO's) of Peshawar, KPK, Pakistan and then to compare them with those of United States, United Kingdom, China and India to find out similar work stressors. A sample size of 100 employees is taken from the social sector, Peshawar, KPK. Primary data is collected through adopted questionnaire listing seven demographics and twenty stressors at work which are derived from literature based on the above mention regions and descriptive, frequencies and crosstabs tests are used for analysis through SPSS. The results shows that Salary, Workload, Peer Support, Working Conditions, Career Growth, Job Loss, Job Security, Supervisors Behavior, Diplomacy, Communication Barrier are the top ten stressors at work place in the social sector. While in comparison, top two stressors i.e. salary and workload are same as that of China, United States and UK while in India, the top two stressors are work-life-balance and lack of supervisory support. The research also brought us to the conclusion that in social sector, both male and female face the above mentioned factors at workplace, mostly from 27-30 years of age group belonging to functional area of the management of the NGO's, INGO's and CBO's. Salary, which is considered to be the biggest motivator, even employees whose current salary of 30-50 thousand also faces salary as major stressor as compare to those who are in range 10-30 thousand rupees. It means that an increase or decrease in the salary or experience does not change the perception of the respondent about the salary as major stressor at work place.

Key words: Stressors, Social Sector, NGO, INGO, CBO

Introduction

Background: Stress is a state of body that cannot be ignored we all get affected by different type of stressors at workplace. The HSE (Health and Safety Executive UK) define stress as a condition or a situation in which an individual realizes some sort of pressure on himself, that may be because of the requirements of the situation or may be because of the incapability of the individual to handle the situation or not being able to cope with the condition, and if continued for a period time then it may cause trouble for the stress occupant.

Stress means pushing something beyond its capabilities. Consider a rubber band which has a certain limit of elasticity. When that limit is crossed, it breaks. Same is the case in human beings. Stress is a state of mind that reflects certain biochemical reactions in the human body and is projected by a sense of anxiety, tension and depression and is caused by such demands by the environment forces or internal forces that cannot be met by the resources available to the person (Devi, 2012).

Work stress is defined as the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when job requirements do not match the worker's capabilities, resources, and needs (National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health 1999).

Stress is the force, pressure, or tension subjected upon an individual who resists these forces and attempt to uphold its true state. In other words we can say that stress is a reaction to an output which is demanded from an individual that is beyond his capabilities and he might starting to get worry about it or he might cannot deal with it (Seyle, 1936). Stress has both positive and negative outcomes. If we look at the positive side, exerting pressure on one self can lead to a better performance e.g. an athlete, he has to push beyond the measure of his stamina to run and win. Similarly a film star has to push him/her acting capabilities in order to perform well. Pressure or stress has many sources and the might pose a big problem if they continue for a long period or they become too frequent or the source of stress is too big and the person is unable to adjust with it. If these requirements are huge and continue for a longer period of time without any interval mental, physical or behavioral problems may occur, (Health & Safety Executive UK).

If a person is under stress due to some reasons, he needs time to recover because it is necessary for the mental state to get stabilized and perform its function properly. Mostly we can see that a worker who is less healthy, unmotivated, unproductive and unsafe or less safe at work place is stressed worker. And these types of business organizations are likely to get successful in the market place.

Scope of Study

The scope of the study is limited to the social sector of Peshawar including NGO,

Problem Statement

To compare eastern and western work stressors and to study work stressors in the social sector of Peshawar.

Objective of study

The objective of the study is to find out that:

- Which work stressors are mostly faced by employees at work place?
- Compare those stressors with those of US, UK, China and India.

Significance of study

The study will help to identify potential stressors at work. It will also help the organization to get a better understanding of work stressors and develop strategies to manage and overcome them.

Purpose of study

The purpose of the study is to find out potential stressors at work in Peshawar KPK, Pakistan social sector and to compare them with those of US, UK, China and India.

Research Question

What are the major work stressors in social sector of Peshawar?

Literature Review

Stressors exist in every organization either large or small, the nature of the work and organizations have become so much complex and sophisticated due to which it exists, work place stress that has a significant effect over the employees job performance, and the organizations in UK are trying to cope with this scenario (Anderson, 2003). There are about eleven forces which are used by the researchers to identify the level of work stress. These are organization structure, work environment, work overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, job responsibility, feedback, future growth, participation, keeping technology up to date, being in an innovative role (Anderson R. , 2003). Work Overload is defined as the excessive work or work that is outside one's capacity (Caplan, Robert, Jones, & Kenneth, 1975), Role Ambiguity or is the insufficient information concerning ones powers, authority, responsibilities or duties to perform one's role (Caplan, 1972), Role Conflict is when the supervisors or subordinates place or expect any contradictory demands from the individual (Beehr, Jex, Stacy, & Murray, 2000), Job Responsibility is the responsibility for people, well-being works, job security, and professional development of an employee (French and Caplan, 1972), Participation is the extent to which an employee has an influence over decisions relevant to his or hers job (Kasl, 1973), Lack of Feedback is not knowing about how you are actually performing. Every employee is expert in his own way until and unless he is told how is performing (Adams, 1980), Technology is to keeping the organization up to date with the latest technology to cop up with new work stressors so that efficiency does not get effected. Latest technology can also be used in information processing (Ginzburg, 1967), being in an innovative role is like you have to be creative and look for improvement in the organization like what can possibly be improved (Kahn, Wolfe, Quinn, Snoek, & Rosenthal, 1964), Future Growth: Impact of status dissimilarity, lack of job security, let down ambition (Brook, 1973), and finally the factor of Recent episodic events that may include life events, like divorce and sadness, which are very stressful (Adams, 1980). The HSE (Health and Safety Executive) is a United Kingdom Governmental firm that looks after the health and safety of the labor force. This group conducted a research in order to establish a workplace stress criteria that was called as the management standards for work related stress (Health and Safety Executives, 2012). Their research consist about six factors (job demand, change in the work place, working relationships, job control, supervisory support and role clarity) (Kerr, McHugh, & McCrory, 2009). According to the National Labor Force Survey (LFS), stress contributes as a largest factor of work-related illness of the workers and the main activities that contribute to stress are

workload: which is associated with tight deadlines, too much work, pressure and responsibility, lack of managerial support and violence at work: which is associated with threats and bullying. Stress is in every organization and varies from levels of management effecting the job satisfaction. Stress reduces the urge of employees to perform better regarding time and working for long hours (Rose, 2003). Low support from the management also increases stress in employees (Stamper & Johlke, 2003).

In the near past, the unemployment rate might have been dropped in the United States but the work stress is rising as the new survey report shows that almost eight in ten employees are stressed out at work mostly by poor pay and excessive workload. These factors are considered to be on the top priority of the work stressors (Sibug, Neal, & Joanne, 2013). The third annual survey conducted by Harris Interactive on the behalf of Everest College polled about 1019 American employees through telephone, which resulted a significant increase in work stress from last year stress survey that was 73 percent. For the current year it was recorded as 83 percent and the rest of the 17 percent said nothing about factors that caused them work stress (Sibug, Neal, & Joanne, 2013). Decreased unemployment means more hiring, but the workers are still stressed out due to years of economic crisis that caused long working hours, budget cuts, and layoffs. According to the survey spokesperson John Swarts, anxiety among different employees is natural now because it is rooted in our working lives, so ones cannot avoid the work pressure so it is important to understand better and new ways about how to cope with pressure. The statistics of the work stress survey showed that poor compensation and unreasonable workload were the top priority work stressors with 14 percent of the worker reporting about lower pay checks and 14 percent of them reported workload as the top priority work stressor, which was an increase of 9 percent from the last year (Sibug, Neal, & Joanne, 2013), relationships with boss and coworkers both were at 11 percent, working In a non-career job was at 8 percent, poor work life balance showed a 7 percent stress, lack of opportunity and career growth was about 6 percent and worry of being fired was about 4 percent (Sibug, Neal, & Joanne, 2013). Work to family conflicts is also a cause which creates stress in employees of an organization (Anderson, Coffey, & Byerly, 2002) and job stress has been viewed as an environmental stimulus to an individual that is dysfunctional for organizations and their members (Kahn, Wolfe, Quinn, Snoek, & Rosenthal, 1964). Other than that, if the organization or the management group does not appreciate or give feedback on the hard work of employee or his contribution towards the organization creates work stress and mostly creates the intention is quitting the job (Stamper & Johlke, 2003).

A survey conducted by Business Consultancy Regus more than half of the organizational employees are stressed at work. The survey polled about 16000 employees around the globe and identified that there were professional not personal reasons behind there stress (Kao, 2012). According to a cross sectional research, It was known that work stress and motivation at work are the best indicators of job satisfaction (Li, Li, & Wang, 2014). The study aimed to examine the levels of motivation and work stress and to know there contribution to job satisfaction. The results of the study indicated that wages and benefits contributed to work stress at a highest rank, followed by the work task and Role ranks. Frequently mentioned stressors included low compensation, too much work load and a very few career opportunities (Li, Li, & Wang, 2014). Recently a massive rural-urban migration took place in china, and the immigrants are considered as to be smokers and are suspected to be having health problems (Cui, Rockett, Yang, & Cao, 2012). A study was conducted in order to examine any association if existed between perceived work related stress and perceived life stress wit smoking behavior among the group during the period of immigration. Perceived work related stress covered the factors of working hours, workload, relationship with co-workers and boos, low salary, delay in receipt of payment of wage, working conditions, and job insecurity. (Cui, Rockett, Yang, & Cao, 2012). The results showed that about 25% of the migrants said that low salary was the highest source of work related stress.

According to a survey, the Indian employees ranked poor work life balance, lack of support, uneven workloads inside work groups and role ambiguity as the top reasons for stress at workplace (Indian Employers Rank Stress No 1 Lifestyle Risk Factor, 2014). Similarly another study, stress at work is quoted as the major issue in both social and corporate sector. There have been a lot of changes in the workplace during the past many years (Kumar & MADHU, 2012). The study identified (Demand, Control, Managers Support, Peer Support,

Relationship Role and Change) as the causes of stress at work. Another study was conducted on call centers in India which showed the promotion opportunities, work feedback, and workload as highly ranked work stressors and change (at workplace), working conditions, workplace politics, job satisfaction, job security as medium ranked stressors (Latha & Panchanatham, 2010).

Methodology

Research Approach

The research can be quantitative and qualitative in nature. Quantitative research normally works on numerical data and use statistical analysis to conclude meaningful results. While qualitative technique seeks to obtain analysis rather than data in works and concepts quantification (Punch, 2005). Both of approaches are have merits and demerits. This research is totally based on quantitative research in which data was collected via questionnaire and the numerical data was then analyzed through different statistical tools and techniques.

Research Design and Method

This research is quantitative in nature; the quantitative techniques are used in this type of research. The numerical data, statistical tools and techniques are used to analyze data. The adopted questionnaire was used for the collection of primary data.

Population

The population selected for study is the social sector of Peshawar which includes NGO (Non-Government Organization), INGO (International Non-Government Organization) and CBO (Community Based Organizations).

Sampling technique and data sample

A cluster sampling and convenient sampling technique was used to collect data. About 150 questionnaires were distributed among the respondents and fully completed 100 questionnaires were received back.

Data collection

For the research primary data was needed which was collected through questionnaires

Data analysis

SPSS version 16 was used for data feeding and the analysis of data.

Statistical test to be used

For the study descriptive, frequencies and cross tabs tests were used for the purpose of analysis of data. In addition, reliability test was used in order to determine that the data is normal and the questionnaire is valid enough.

Table 1 Potential Stressors Identified

UNITED KINGDOM	UNITED STATES	CHINA	INDIA
Work Load	Salary	Compensation	Work-life Balance
Lack of Managerial Support	Work Load	Work Load	Lack of Supervisory Support
Violence at Work	Relation with Boss	Career Opportunities	Lack of Management Support
Organization structure	Relation with Co-workers	Working Hours	Workload
Work Environment	Job interest	Relation with Co-workers	Role Ambiguity
Role Conflict	Work-life Balance	Relation with Boss	Job Demand
Role Ambiguity	Career Growth	Delay in wage	Job Control
Job Responsibility	Lack of Opportunity	Working Conditions	Promotional Opportunities
Feed Back	Job Loss	Job Security	Feedback
Future Growth	Feed Back		Working Conditions
Participation	Lack of Organizational support		Workplace Politics
Technology	Lack of Management support		Job Security
Innovative Role	Working Responsibility		Change in workplace
Job Demand			
Working Relationships			
Job Control			
Supervisory Support			

Analysis

Reliability Test

To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the collected data from 28 respondents and used reliability test. According to the results of Cronbach's Alpha value 0.518 shows that the questionnaire is reliable for this type of study.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.518	28

Overall descriptive of the data sample

Table 2 Stressors Descriptive

STRESSORS	N
Salary	92
Job Security	86
Work Load	84
Career Growth	82
Working Conditions	66
Job Loss	66
Diplomacy	62
Peers Support	48
Work-Life Balance	48
Working Hours	46
Participation	44
Role Conflict	40
Role Ambiguity	38
Supervisors Behavior	36
Co-Workers Relations	36
Technology	32
Decision Making Process	28
No Time For Social Life	20
No Feedback	26
Communication Barrier	24

The overall descriptive of the data explains that irrespective of ranks, the salary has been marked by 92 respondents, job security by 86 respondents, workload by 84 respondents, career growth by 82 respondents, working conditions by 66 respondents and so on. This makes salary is the highest discussed stressors among the respondents.

Analysis of Stressors by Ranking and Frequency

Table 3 Stressors Frequency and Ranking

RANKINGS	STRESSORS	FREQUENCIES
1	Salary	32
2	Workload	22
3	Peers Support	16
4	Working Conditions	14
5	Career Growth	16
6	Job Loss	14
7	Job Security	14
8	Supervisors Behavior	10
9	Diplomacy	12
10	Communication Barrier	10

By running a frequency test we came to know about our desired top 10 work stressors, ranking from 1 to 10, with the help of the frequencies and now we can easily identify that how many of the respondents marked the stressor on the given rank. Salary was ranked as no 1 stressor by 32 respondents, followed by workload as second by 22 respondents, peer support as 3rd by 16 respondents, working condition, career growth, job loss, job

security, supervisor’s behavior, diplomacy and communication barrier as 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th by 14, 16, 14, 14, 10, 12 and finally 10 respondents.

Crosstab and Correlation

In this step we used crosstab stressors with demographics (gender, age group designation, type of organization, marital status, work experience and current salary of the respondents in order to get more detail understanding of the stressors.

4.4.1 Stressors with Demographics

Table 4: For this analysis consider the table given below:

R	STRESSORS	FRQ	GENDE R		AGE GROUP					DESIGNATION			ORGANIZATION TYPE		
			M	F	22- 26	27- 30	31- 34	35- 38	39- 42	Fun c	Supr	Mgr	NG O	ING O	CB O
1	Salary	32	16	16	6	20	0	6	0	24	8	0	18	6	8
2	Workload	22	10	12	6	12	0	4	4	12	6	2	14	0	8
3	Peers Supp	16	8	8	2	12	0	2	0	6	10	0	8	4	4
4	Working Condit	14	10	4	0	6	8	0	0	10	4	0	2	10	2
5	Career Growth	16	12	4	0	6	8	2	0	10	2	4	6	6	4
6	Job Ls	14	4	10	2	12	0	0	0	10	2	2	8	2	4
7	Job Security	14	10	4	2	6	2	4	0	10	4	0	12	2	0
8	Supervisor Behavior	10	2	8	2	4	4	0	0	6	2	2	0	4	6
9	Diplomacy	12	10	2	0	4	2	0	0	6	4	2	0	6	6
10	Communication Barrier	10	2	10	2	4	2	2	0	2	4	4	4	4	2

MARITAL STATUS		WORKING EXPERIENCE (MONTHS)						CURRENT SALARY (THOUSANDS)					
S	M	6- 12	13- 18	19- 24	25- 30	31- 36	Over 36	10- 30	30-50	50-70	70-90	90-110	Over 110
18	14	2	10	4	2	6	8	8	20	4	0	0	0
12	10	4	4	2	4	4	4	10	10	2	0	0	0
8	8	0	2	4	0	4	6	6	6	4	0	0	0
10	4	0	2	0	2	0	10	2	4	8	0	0	0
8	8	2	2	0	2	2	8	6	2	8	0	0	0
6	8	2	0	6	2	2	2	6	6	2	0	0	0
4	10	2	0	4	4	0	4	4	8	2	0	0	0
6	4	0	2	0	0	2	6	2	4	4	0	0	0
8	4	0	0	2	0	0	10	2	8	2	0	0	0
4	6	0	2	0	2	4	2	0	6	4	0	0	0

Gender

If we look at the gender, the male category faced salary and career growth as the major stressors at work place, workload, working conditions, job security and diplomacy as medium stressors and finally peers support, job loss, supervisory behavior and communication barrier as low stressors while the female category in addition faced salary and workload as the major, job loss and communication barrier as the medium and finally peer support, working condition, career growth, job security, supervisory behavior and diplomacy as lower stressor at work place.

Age Group

If we look at the age groups, the group from 22-26 years faces salary, work load and peer support as the major stressors at work. A similar reaction was seen from group of 27-30 just in addition to job loss and from group 35-38. The age group of 31-34 did not faced the above mentioned stressors but working hours, career growth, job security, supervisory behavior, diplomacy and working condition as lower stressors.

Designation

Most of the employees of the functional area faced salary, workload and peers support as major stressors followed by working conditions, career growth, job loss and job security as lower stressors. Similar result came from few supervisors but at managerial level no respondent mentioned salary as a major stressor but few faced workload as major one.

Type of Organization

Most of the employees of the NGO's and CBO's faced salary, workload as major stressors and job security as lower stressors at workplace as compare INGO's where only few respondents faced salary as major stressor.

Marital Status

Based on the marital status many of the single respondents faced salary and workload as the major stressors at work place. Only a few number less, the married respondents also mentioned these as the major ones. For the female respondents job security was also a stressor but at lower state.

Working Experience

There were few respondents that faced salary and work load as major stressors during their course of experience. Only a distinctive number of respondents with experience of 13-18 month face salary as major and with an experience of over 36 month, respondents faced working condition as medium and diplomacy as lower stressor at work place

Current Salary

A few respondents with current salary ranging from 10-30 and 50-70 thousand rupees faced salary as stressors, but most among this category faced workload as major stressor at work. Most of the respondents who were in 30-50 thousand rupees range faced salary and workload as the major stressor. Unfortunately there were no respondents for the range of 70 thousand to over 110 thousand rupees.

Discussion

The research tells us about major stressors at work place. We studied major stressors of the United States, United Kingdom, China, and India. Based on our research we came to know that in social sector of Peshawar (NGO's, INGO's, CBO's) Salary, Workload and Peers Support are the top three ranked stressors followed by Working Conditions, Career Growth, Job Loss, Job Security, Supervisors Behavior, Diplomacy and Communication Barrier at the lowest rank respectively. If we compare our results with the table 4, our top 2 stressor are same as that of the United States and china, while in United Kingdom, workload is on top priority and lack of managerial support or peers support is on the second priority, while in India the most faced work stressors are the work-life balance on top priority followed by lack of supervisory and management support and the employee puts workload on fourth priority respectively.

Conclusion

The top ranked stressors in the social sector are salary, workload, peer support and so etc. The genders face the above mentioned factors at workplace, mostly from 27-30 years of age group belonging to functional area of the management of the NGO's, INGO's and CBO's. Respondents, who are by status single and are having an

experience of 13-18 months face these stressors more as compare to those who are married and are with an experience of over 36 months, even whose current salary of 30-50 thousand also faces salary as major stressor as compare to those who are in range of 10-30 thousand rupees. It means that an increase or decrease in the salary or experience does not change the perception of the respondent about the salary as major stressor at work place.

Recommendations

- The questionnaire used for this study is suitable for descriptive studies hence it can be used for further studies
- Test used in this studies are best for descriptive studies
- To find more concrete results the sample size must be expanded in order to get more generalized results
- The study can be done not only in social sector but also can be done in public and private sectors.
- More work is required in future to find out more stressors in work environment.

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Appendix: Questionnaire

Work stress survey questionnaire

Confidentiality note: The data collected will be treated as strictly confidential and used for academic purposes only

1. Informed consent (*purpose and time frame explained to the interview and agreed upon*)
 - Yes
 - No

2. Gender of the responded
 - Male
 - Female

3. Age group
 - 22 – 26
 - 27 – 30
 - 31 – 34
 - 35 – 38
 - 39 – 42
 - More than 42

4. Designation: _____

5. Type of organization:
 - Non-Government Organization
 - International Non-Government Organization (INGO)
 - Community based Organization (CBO)

6. Marital status
 - Married
 - Single

7. Working experience of the respondent
 - 6 months – 12 months
 - 13 months – 18 months
 - 19 months – 24 months
 - 25 months – 30 months
 - 31 months – 36 months
 - More than 36 months

8. Current salary (monthly)
 - 10,000 – 30,000

- 30,001- 50,000
- 50,001 – 70,000
- 70,001 – 90,000
- 90,101 – 110,000
- More than 110,000

9. Below is the list of 20 potential indicators that can lead to work related stress. You are requested to rank from 1 to 10 as high or low the top ten indicators with respect to your job, job description and working environment.

S.No	Work Stressors	Your Top 10 Stressors
1	Working Conditions	
2	Work Load	
3	Salary/compensation	
4	Supervisor behavior	
5	Lack of support from peers	
6	Role conflict	
7	Role ambiguity	
8	Career growth	
9	Diplomacy	
10	Participation	
11	No feedback	
12	Communication barrier	
13	Relation with Co-workers	
14	Working Hours	
15	Work-life Balance	
16	Technology	
17	No time for social life	
18	Job Security	
19	Decision making processes	
20	Job Loss	

The generalized (top level) results can be shared on request and prior approval from the Institute for your consumption. Thank you for your time and patience